

Reducing Damage Deformation for Earthquake Resistant Building

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ABSTRACT

Earthquake, as a natural phenomenon that can bring enormous energy, usually causes buildings collapses and has brought great losses to human beings in recent years, so seismic design is closely related to social stability and economic development. As a basic kind of building structure, frame has been prevalent in our daily life, so the seismic resistant design of frame structure becomes essential. This paper firstly introduces a preliminary understanding of this phenomenon of earthquake, analyzes the forms of damage of frame structures caused by earthquake, and then analyzes the updates of Chinese seismic design codes and the specific measures corresponding to earthquake hazards (shock absorber/damper, seismic isolation), finally makes a prospect for the development of seismic design in the future.

1. Introduction

Earthquake is a kind of natural phenomenon which can release strong energy. It is very destructive. Without effective protective measures, it will cause great losses of personnel and property. The 7.9-magnitude earthquake that struck Wenchuan in 2008, for example, killed 87,587 people and caused losses totaling RMB 845.1 billion. The earthquake itself poses little threat to people, and people cannot be directly killed by it, but the chain reaction produced by it, such as building collapse, flood and fire, can be deadly. And building collapse is the most important cause of death. According to the statistics, 95% of the deaths in the earthquake are caused by the collapse of buildings, so the seismic design of buildings is a key element in the structural design of buildings.

Since the 21st century, as the traditional seismic design is not strong enough to withstand

large earthquakes, compared with the traditional seismic design, researchers have developed a series of highly applicable earthquake resistant measures with low cost and remarkable effect, the most typical measures among which are shock absorption and seismic isolation. Because these two techniques have great advantages over the traditional seismic resistant methods, so they have a good prospect and have become the first trend in the development of seismic design. In this paper, the seismic damage and the significance of seismic design of structures are introduced firstly, and the techniques of structural shock absorption and isolation are introduced further. Finally, the prospect of seismic design is put forward.

2. Seismic Damage of Frame Structure

For the frame structure, the main damages of the frame structure in the earthquake include column damage, beam damage and beam-column joint damage [1].

(1) Column damage: In the frame structure, the column damage is arguably the most common and is generally greater than the beam and more serious than that one. The column, receiving seismic waves before the beam, is more vulnerable to be damaged than the beam. In addition, the reinforcement at the beam end is more than that at the column end, which causes the smaller bearing capacity of the column than that of the beam. Under earthquake, the inter-layer displacement of the

column is larger, which leads to the occurrence of plastic hinges before the beam and the occurrence of mechanism of strong beam and weak column, making the damage appearing at the end of column more easily. The main reason for the column damage is that the stirrup at the end of the column is not enough or the diameter of the stirrup is small, so the bearing capacity of the column is small[2]. The main manifestation of the seismic damage received by the column end is that the damage of the top of the column is worse than the bottom of the column, the junction of the top of the column and the beam is particularly serious, the end of the column appears plastic hinge and the buckling of the rebar exposed. Horizontal crack appears at the bottom of column, the concrete falls off and is crushed, the longitudinal bar is buckling and exposed, and the stirrup is twisted. The other phenomenon include “the damage of the corner column is worse than that of the inner column” and “the damage of the short column is worse than that of the long column”, and most of which are shear damage. Usually, the upper part is fractured which appears oblique cracks, while the lower part is dislocated. The concrete is peeled and crushed, and the steel bar is exposed. Because the upper end of the column is less constrained than the lower end, the upper end of the column is more

vulnerable to the earthquake. In the same way, the corner column is more severely damaged than the inner column because the former, on the outermost of the building, is less constrained than the latter. If the column is long, the allowable deflection becomes large. Under the earthquake, the displacement of the left and right swing is larger than that of the short column, so the damage from the earthquake is less than that of the short column.

Figure 1. Seismic Damage of Frame Structure

(2) Beam damage: The damage of the beam also occurs at the beam end. Under the earthquake, the tensile strength of the concrete is less than the tensile stress received, which results in the formation of cracks. If the earthquake is serious, the internal reinforcement will yield, and the angle of the section will increase sharply. If there are not enough stirrups at the beam end, the shear force caused by the earthquake will lead to cracks and even fractures[1].

(3) Joint damage: The last one is the damage of the joint. The joint is liable to produce large shear force and pressure under the earthquake. When the shear force is too high, the damage of the concrete will happen before the stirrup yield, which leads to the displacement of the structure and inclination[1].

In addition to the three main damages above, there are the damages of the stairway, the filling wall and the envelop enclosure.

(4) Stairway damage: parts of the damage occur in the stairway, the concrete of the stair support is crushed, the longitudinal bar of the floor is exposed and even broken. There is a huge horizontal crack in the middle of the stair, and the concrete of the stair beam is peeled off. Because the stair is designed as a single component, and the displacement and force of the stair in coordination with the main structure under the earthquake are not taken into account in the seismic design of the whole structure, so the collapse of the stair is very common[3].

Figure 2. Seismic Damage of Stairway in a Frame Structure

Damage of the filling wall and the envelop enclosure: extensive damage mainly occurs in the envelop structure and filling wall. The main forms of damage are cracks on the wall surface along the perimeter of the column, oblique or cross cracks on the wall between windows, and horizontal cracks on the wall under the window, more seriously, damage appears as the crush of the part of the wall[1]. The interior of the frame structure is filled with walls and enclosures, and this kind of structure is the main seismic resistant factor in the frame structure. Therefore, the filling wall will change the distribution of the story shear of the structure and bear most of the horizontal shear force, so that the horizontal shear force of the main structure of the frame will be reduced and the damage of the main structure will be reduced. In addition, the stiffness of the filled wall is very large, which decreases the horizontal deformation of the frame structure, weakening the layer displacement and the whiplash effect. Due to the existence of the filling wall and envelop structure, structural damage following “strong column and weak beam” rule seldom occurs[4]. On the other hand, as the frame structure is flexible and the filling wall is rigid, the deformation of the two structures are inconsistent under the earthquake, and if there is no effective connection at the joint, the shear damage and crushing of the wall will occur.

Macroscopically, the lower part of the frame structure suffered less damage in earthquake, but the slight whipping effect appeared. However, the upper layer of building usually protrudes, the concrete cracks, and the horizontal crack appears between the main structure and the concrete. Because of the small mass and stiffness of the protruding part of the building compared with the main part, the acceleration and displacement are larger under the earthquake, resulting in the whipping effect[5].

3. Seismic Design

3.1 Overview of Seismic Design

Seismic design is a kind of design to meet the economic and safety requirements of building structure under the earthquake. The first way to resist or weaken the effects of earthquake is to use codes to design buildings, which is called seismic design codes.

3.2 Shock Absorption

Earthquake is an energy-releasing natural phenomenon. The damage of buildings is the result of the energy released by the earthquake on buildings. Now, measures to reduce the damage of earthquake to buildings include adding shock-absorbing structures to buildings. Shock absorption refers to installing or adding some energy-dissipating components with strong deformation capacity (such as a support, a shear wall, a connector, etc.) in buildings, or installing devices in some parts of structures, such as an interlayer, a joint, etc. When the earthquake occurs, the energy transmitted from the epicenter to the building can be converted into heat energy to consume the seismic energy, thereby reducing the response generated by the structure. In the case of smaller earthquake, shock absorbers can increase the overall stiffness of the building while the building remains elastic. When a high-magnitude earthquake occurs, the lateral deformation of the energy dissipation device prior to the structure become inelastic, thus prevent the main structure from being inelastic.

Shock absorbers are usually composed of dampers. At present, there are two main types of dampers:

(1) Displacement damper: The effect of displacement damper is mainly related to the displacement produced by buildings when the earthquake occurs. The greater the displacement, the better the effect. This damper usually includes metal damper and friction damper. The metal damper can consume energy through the elastoplasticity of their own material. The results were shown that the metal damper have large damping, small displacement and stable energy dissipation. In the frame structure, the inter-story drift can be reduced and the damage between the wall and the beam joint can be reduced, which can effectively reduce the risk of beam, column and joint damage and the whipping effect in the earthquake. However, the yield limit of such damper cannot be adjusted and cannot be changed once set, which makes the damper unable to adapt to different earthquakes. The friction damper is used for friction energy dissipation through two relatively moving

components. When the earthquake occurs, the damper can increase the stiffness of the structure and shorten the period of self-vibration, thus reducing the response of the structure, such as layer displacement and layer shear. The friction damper just as the metal damper, cannot meet the energy dissipation requirements of different earthquakes. Due to the fact of simple manufacture of displacement dampers and its highly effective energy dissipation with bilinear hysteretic characteristics, it is stable and has high cost performance[6].

(2) Velocity dampers: Velocity dampers refer to those whose damping and relative motion constitutes a functional relationship. The principle of action is similar to piston motion as they are made based on the principle that the pressure difference between the front and rear of the piston causes the fluid to pass through the orifice to generate damping force [7]. Their shock absorption capacity is proportional to the velocity, the faster the deformation is, the greater the damping force is, and then the better the overall effect of the damper is. Velocity dampers mainly include viscoelastic dampers and viscous dampers. Among them, viscous dampers are devices that convert the kinetic energy of a fluid into thermal energy through the pores of a viscous liquid to consume energy. The type of liquid in viscous dampers can decide their shock absorption performance. The higher the viscosity of the liquid is, the better the effect is. The common liquid medium includes hydraulic oil, silicone oil and so on. In addition, this kind of damper is also affected by excitation frequency, external temperature and relative velocity. Compared with displacement dampers, this kind of damper can adapt to earthquakes with different magnitude, increase the damping of structures without changing the period of structures, reduce layer displacement, inter-story drift and base shear under the seismic loads. Viscoelastic dampers refer to energy-dissipation devices that use some high-molecular polymers with both elastic and viscous properties as an energy-dissipation material, such as silicon. Such viscoelastic materials are usually fixed directly to vibrating components, or installed between two components, to dissipate energy through their motion relative to the two components [6].

Shock absorption greatly reduces the deformation of the structure under earthquakes, thus ensuring that the non-structural components are not catastrophically damaged by earthquakes. In this kind of seismic design, the non-bearing device in the structure can quickly consume the energy generated by earthquakes and protect the main structure from damage.

3.3 Seismic Isolation

Currently, seismic isolation is an extremely popular seismic design. During the effect of an earthquake, the superstructure, including columns, beams and walls, undergoes a large displacement. The seismic isolation, through adding the isolation layer composed of isolation devices (bearings, dampers) in the foundation or interlayer, adopts the isolation devices to block the propagation of seismic waves so as to weaken and dissipate the energy transmitted by earthquakes to the building and prolong the period of natural vibration of the upper structure, finally reduce the response of the superstructure during the earthquake.

Isolated structures are more capable of weakening the building's response under earthquakes than shock absorption structures. According to statistics, in the 2011 earthquake of the Pacific coast of Tōhoku, only 5% of people died due to buildings collapses, leaving the superstructure of all the isolated buildings largely intact. And only 15% of the isolated buildings had their seismic isolation devices damaged. Moreover, the seismic response of the isolation structure is 67% - 84% less than that of the structure with traditional seismic design, so the seismic isolation has become the main seismic design blueprint at present. Also, the seismic isolated structure is more economical and practical compared with the structures installed with shock absorbers. Presently, most buildings in China are mainly reinforced concrete structures, and seismic isolation is widely used.

Due to the advancement of science and society, the types of rubber bearings are now various. The seismic isolation device is primarily divided into three categories:

(1) Laminated Steel Plate Rubber Bearing: This is the most commonly used bearing in seismic isolation, mainly composed of rubber and multi-layer steel plates. The thin steel plate is sandwiched between the rubber layers, increasing the period of the upper structure and providing a certain damping so as to increase the vertical stiffness of the whole structure. It cannot only reduce the horizontal seismic effects but also bear the vertical load on the superstructure. In addition, the inner of the bearing is provided with a lead core, which has the function of enhancing lateral stiffness and shock absorption [8]. In terms of mechanical properties, the isolation rubber bearing has high compression performance, equivalent to the reinforced concrete column with the same cross-section, while the tensile performance is only one-tenth of the compression performance. From the point of view of durability, the durability of the bearing depends on rubber materials, and the use of special-processing rubber materials can enormously improve its durability. However, this kind of bearing cannot

produce damping effect with respect to vertical earthquakes, and there is a danger of resonance for buildings with long natural period, thus this kind of bearing has a good effect for low-rise buildings.

Figure4. Laminated Rubber Bearing

(2) Helical spring bearing: This kind of bearing is mainly composed of spiral springs. The metal spring acts as a rolling bearing and can withstand certain amount of displacement and shear force. However, because of its low vertical stiffness, lateral stiffness and small damping, its performance is not quite good under strong earthquakes, so it requires to be used with dampers [8].

(3) Sliding & rolling bearing: The rolling sliding bearing is a device that takes the upper structure as a whole and sets a sliding material with a very small friction coefficient in the seismic isolation layer, which causes friction through the relative sliding between the upper structure and the lower structure and converts the energy transmitted by the earthquakes upward into heat energy so as to effectively mitigate the impact of the earthquakes [8]. Its dynamic characteristic is that the natural period of the whole system is the same as the structural period before sliding, the stiffness of the isolation layer becomes small, and the natural period of the whole system becomes large after sliding. Therefore, the sliding & rolling bearing can avoid the resonance effect caused by most earthquakes. Typically, sliding & rolling bearing includes graphite cushion sliding bearing, sand cushion sliding bearing and so on. As this kind of bearing needs to bear all the load of the upper structure during the earthquake, if the upper load is too large, it will affect its effectiveness of energy dissipation. It also cannot be self-reset, so researchers have developed a kind of sliding & rolling which

can reset by itself, such as, Frictional Pendulum System (FPS) [8]. FPS can rely on its own gravity to reset, and the friction slider relies on its own gravity and sliding surface contact friction to generate thermal energy, thereby consuming energy to reduce the seismic response.

Figure5. Sliding Bearing

Conclusion

Earthquake, as a kind of natural phenomenon which can bring a lot of energy and have great destructiveness, since the 21st century, still accompanies with the development of human society. As the development of economy and science, seismic measures have been increasingly put forward, among which two most effective methods are shock absorption and seismic isolation, playing an important role in It plays a huge role in sudden earthquakes that exceed the design intensity. Compared with seismic isolation, shock absorption can be used in a wide range of applications, not only earthquake-resistant but also wind-resistant. While in terms of seismic isolation, it is featured by economy, simple design and better seismic resistant effect. The two methods can not completely replace each other but compose the complementary relationship. Throughout the history of seismic isolation and shock absorption, the United States and Japan lead their application. Since the beginning of the 21st century, China has been widely applying seismic isolation and shock absorption on various newly built structures, such as Kunming Changshui International Airport, China Exposition Exhibition Hall, etc. [9]. Because of their significant effect on earthquake resistance, construction funds and maintenance funds are indirectly reduced. Seismic isolation and shock

absorption ensure the safety of people's lives and promote the development of society, so they have great prospects. China should vigorously develop highly effective seismic design methods such as seismic isolation to lay a solid foundation for the development of social economy.

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